

AN ASSESSMENT OF WOUND DRESSING BY NURSING PERSONNEL AT OLABISI ONABANJO UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL (O.O.U.T.H.) SHAGAMU, OGUN STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: A variety of effects may result in the occurrence of a wound which may result in immediate loss of all or part of organ functioning, sympathetic stress response, hemorrhage and blood clotting, bacterial contamination and death of cells. Careful asepsis is the most important factor in keeping these effects to a minimum and promoting the successful care of wounds which is dependent on the nurse's knowledge and understanding of normal wound healing physiology, method of closure and the optimal treatment of the wound and with this knowledge, nurses can provide a systematic and holistic patient assessment, and consider any potential wound related complications (Vuolo JC 2006).

Aim: This investigation aimed to assess wound dressing performances among nursing personnel in the three surgical wards of Olabisi Onabanjo University Teaching Hospital (O.O.U.T.H.) Shagamu Ogun State Nigeria.

Methodology: The investigators utilized the descriptive method of research. A total of sixty nursing personnel in the male, female, and paediatric surgical wards were randomly selected for the investigation. Performance of wound dressing was assessed through an investigators formulated questionnaire and evaluation checklist based on the concept of sterile wound dressing technique.

Results: Nurses have a very good performance of wound dressing as they applied the concepts/principles of sterile technique in the performance of the procedure. There was no significant difference between nurses in the performance of wound dressing and their demographic variables such as age, gender, religion, and educational qualification. However, significant difference was found between length of clinical experience and practice of wound dressing.

Conclusion: Findings suggests a relationship between length of clinical experience and practice of good wound dressing. Hence regular seminars on wound dressing should be organized to refresh nurses and keep them up to date in nursing practice.

KEYWORDS: Surgical wound, dressing procedure, nursing personnel, assessment, infection.

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INTRODUCTION

The performance of surgery leads to the disruption of the integrity and protective barriers of the skin thereby exposing deep body tissues to pathogens present in the environment, predisposing the patient to the risk of infection at the surgical site. Despite the advances in surgical techniques, the incidence of postoperative wound infection continues to be a challenge in our health facilities.

A comparative study was conducted in Australia on wound infection account in hospital. The study showed that 38% of wound infections also occurred in the hospital with all hospital acquired infections (HAIs)(Ford D, Koehler S. 2005).

Healthcare-Associated Infections (HCAIs) are a matter of priority for the NHS. They are associated with significant morbidity, and frequently lead to increased length of hospital stay, pain and discomfort for the patient, and in some cases even permanent disability. It is estimated that surgical site infections (SSIs) constitute around 14% of all HCAIs. Any break in the skin affords a portal of entry for microbial pathogens, and hence places the patient at an increased risk of infection. To address the issue, a multi-factorial strategy for the prevention of SSIs is essential, with postoperative dressings playing a key part alongside universal precautions such as hand hygiene and aseptic technique. The available guidance specifies the need for a postoperative dressing which provides an effective physical barrier and a moist environment for optimal wound healing. Vapour-permeable barrier dressings appear to be effective in meeting both of these criteria and also offer additional advantages both to patients and practitioners, such as patient comfort and the ability to stay in place whilst the patient showers (Downie , Egdell , Bielby, Searle 2010).

Hospital acquired infections present a serious hazard to patients, and are a significant legal and economic liability to healthcare institutions and the community.

Surgical site infections (SSI's) have been reported to be one of the most common causes of nosocomial infections and account for 20% to 25% of all nosocomial infections worldwide and that 2–5% of all patients who undergo an operation will develop an SSI (Martone and Nicholas 2001)

The observational and sectional study analyzed the quality of the wound dressing procedure performed on hospitalized patients at a medical surgical unit of a University Hospital, based on their classification according to the degree of care dependency and activity performance phases. Using a check list, 168 wound dressings were observed between October and December 2005. Procedure quality was analyzed based on the Positivity Index (IP) and values >70% were considered satisfactory. For the preparation, the IP was 68%, 63%, 73% and 75% for patients with degrees I, II, III and IV, respectively; for execution, 70%, 69%, 71% and 75% and, for unit organization, it was >70% for all degrees. However, the items: validity time frame checking, respect for aseptic principles and maintenance of logical sequence of procedures were compromised. Rigorous execution of procedures allows for risk decrease and assures beneficial results for patients, conferring quality to nursing actions (Nonino, Anselmi, Dalmas 2008). An evaluative study conducted in an acute care St. George hospital Kogarah, India. The study aimed to implement a clinical practice in improvement programme in reducing surgical wound infection by improving the hand washing and wound dressing practices of nurses. The study also aimed to identify the important contributing factors to a model that predicts surgical wound infection. Wounds of 2000 patients were assessed to determine the wound infection rate and severity of wound infection. The hand washing and wound dressing practices of 40 nurses were observed. The results of the study suggest that there was markedly significant reduction in the rate and severity of wound infection following the implementation of intervention (Ancheril 2004).

A comparative study conducted at St. John, New Brunswick, Canada, to assess the effectiveness of sterile and clean wound dressing done since clean dressings have been used instead of sterile dressings for years, with no apparent ill effects. No previous studies have compared the sterility and cost of clean versus sterile dressing materials. Sterility and cost of sterile gauze, panty liners, sanitary napkins, diapers and Coban tape (3M, USA) were compared. Samples, 2 cm x 2 cm in size, were cut out of each material under aseptic conditions, and delivered to the microbiology laboratory in sterile urine containers. The samples were then cultured and organisms were identified using conventional mean. The study concluded that using sterile technique even though costly maintains sterility (Alqahtani, Lalonde 2006).

An evaluative study was conducted in Niagara Community Care Access Centre (CCAC) in Canada. At the beginning of the study, a number of gaps were found in wound management. The clinical management of

wounds was diverse; however, wound care therapies were mostly low-cost dry gauze dressings with creams. Wound management was lacking assessment tools and techniques, evidence-based practice guidelines, advanced dressings, and other tools and therapies for wound-healing (Hurd, Zuiliani, Posnett 2008).

The most commonly used dressings are simple, low-adherent island dressings, but care should be taken as some adhesives can cause reactions in patients with sensitive skin. Blistering may occur if dressings are applied under tension or over a joint where movement will cause friction between skin and dressing [Gupta *et al*, 2002]. The choice of dressing should also be based on the patient's needs. If, for example, the patient is treated as a day case, a shower proof dressing may be most appropriate if it is required for more than 24 hours.

It is the responsibility of the nurse to maintain skin integrity and promote wound healing and to achieve this, nurses must understand the factors affecting skin integrity, the physiology of wound healing, and specific measures that promote optimal skin conditions. One of the specific measures taken by nurses is wound dressing. According to Kozier & Erb's [2012] dressings are applied to protect the wound from mechanical injury, microbial contamination, to provide or maintain moist wound healing and thermal insulation, to absorb drainage or debride a wound or both, to prevent hemorrhage (when applied as a pressure dressing or with elastic bandages) and to splint or immobilize the wound site and thereby facilitate healing and preventing injury.

Successful wound care outcome according to Bowler [2002] depends on the practitioner who knows what to expect in terms of the stages, type of tissue, and timing of normal healing process. Hence it is necessary to assess the performance of wound dressing procedure by nursing personnel.

Purpose of the study

To assess the performance of surgical wound dressing procedure by nursing personnel with the intention to document findings as baseline to improve on the quality of wound dressing performance and nursing care at the Olabisi Onabanjo University Teaching Hospital.

Research Hypotheses

1. There will be no significant difference in the performance of wound dressing procedure between males and females.
2. There will be no significant difference in the performance of wound dressing procedure between student nurses and registered nurses.
3. There will be no relationship between performance of wound dressing procedure and educational background.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design

This is an observational study. Descriptive design was used in the assessment of the performance of wound dressing procedure by nursing personnel.

Research setting

The research was carried out at Olabisi Onabanjo University Teaching Hospital, Shagamu, Ogun State. It is a tertiary health institution approved for use in the training of health care professionals.

Target population

All nursing personnel working in male surgical, female surgical, and paediatric surgical wards at Olabisi Onabanjo University Teaching Hospital, Shagamu.

Sample and Sampling technique

A sample frame of 60 (sixty) nursing personnel was drawn out of the target population using random sampling technique.

Inclusion criteria

The study includes nursing students and staff nurses who carried out wound dressing during the period of study in the male surgical, female surgical and paediatric surgical wards.

Research instrument

The data for the study was collected using a structured observation checklist with nineteen (19) wound dressing procedures drawn from the nursing procedure manual and a self-developed questionnaire for demographic data which consist of demographic information such as age, gender, working experience and educational background. Result of procedure performance is interpreted as follows 16 – 19 as excellent, 13 -15 as very good, 10 – 12 as good and 0 – 9 as needs improvement.

Validity of instrument

The nineteen wound dressing procedures were lifted from the official nursing procedure book of the O.O.U.T.H. (The institution used for the study) and contain standard nursing procedures.

Reliability of instrument

The instrument was pre-tested among similar group sample at the Accident and Emergency Unit of O.O.U.T.H. and was found to be reliable.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical clearance was obtained from O.O.U.T.H. ethical committee prior to the conduct of the investigation. Precautionary measures were taken into consideration to safeguard the study respondents' legal rights. Prior to the interview, consent forms were given to the respondents and have them read and signed it. Confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents were maintained by only a code number on the questionnaire.

METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The collected data was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Descriptive statistics: Mean, standard deviation, frequency and percentage distribution was calculated based on the obtained scores.

Inferential statistics: Chi- square was calculated to find the significant difference in the mean practice scores and to study the relationship between knowledge and practice scores with their selected demographic variables.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows a total of sixty respondents in the study. Majority 48 (78%) were female and 12 (22%) were males. Twenty seven (45 %) were between ages 26 – 35 years. Forty two (70%) of respondents were Christians and 18(30%) were Muslims. Majority of the respondents 42 (70%) of the respondents were student nurses. Thirty three (55%) respondents had working experience of 1 – 3 years. In the basic schools of nursing, students are exposed to wound dressing procedures as early as six (6) months into the programme, hence working experience is built on from six months.

Table 2 showed that in carrying out the procedure, seventy five percent (45) of nursing personnel informed patient of the procedure, 83.3% provided privacy after wheeling trolley to bedside, (50) 83.3% closed nearby windows, (60) 100% arranged bed clothes to access wound for dressing, (33) 55% washed hands under running tap before starting procedure, (16) 26.7% were assisted in the pouring out of lotion. Seventy percent (42) of respondent carefully removed old dressing from wound into kidney dish. Thirty percent (18) of respondents dropped forceps after removal of old dressings, (18)30% of respondents used a pair of dissecting and a 2nd pair of dressing forceps to clean wound with antiseptic lotion from inside to outside of the wound. Fifty five percent (33) of the respondent discarded cotton swabs after each stroke over the wound, (22) 36.7% removed plaster stains after covering wound and before applying plaster. Eighty percent (48) of respondent applied sterile

Table 1 Demographic characteristics of the respondents (n= 60)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
15- 25	19	31.7
26 – 35	27	45.0
36 – 45	10	16.7
46 – 55	3	5.0
> 56	1	1.7
Total	60	100.0
Gender		
Males	13	21.7
Females	47	78.3
Total	60	100.0
Religion		
Christianity	42	70.0
Islam	18	30.0
Total	60	100.0
Educational qualification		
Nursing students	42	70.0
Registered nurse/ midwife	9	15.0
Registered nurse – midwife	6	10.0
Bachelors in nursing science	3	5.0
Total	60	100.0
Years of experience		
1 – 3		
4 – 6	33	55.0
7 – 9	13	21.7
10 – 12	6	10.0
> 13	4	6.7
Total	4	6.7
	60	100.0

Table 2: Performance of wound dressing by respondents N=60

Wound dressing procedures	Yes	No	Total
1) Inform patient about procedure.	45	15	60
2) Wheel trolley to bed and provide privacy.	50	10	60
3) Close nearby windows and switch off fans.	50	10	60
4) The dresser arranges bed clothes in order to gain access to wound	60	0	60
5) Wash hands under running tap.	33	27	60
6) Assistant help to remove lids of bowls and kidney dish on top shelf of trolley and pour out lotion.	16	44	60
7) Dresser takes a pair of dressing forceps and removes soiled dressings into kidney dish for used dressings and swabs.	42	18	60
8) Drop the dressing forceps into kidney dish for used instruments.	18	42	60
9) Using a pair of dissecting forceps and a 2 nd pair dressing forceps, clean wound with antiseptic lotion.	18	42	60
10) Clean wound first then it's surrounding.	59	1	60
11) Discard cotton wool swabs used in cleaning after each stroke over the wound.			
12) Remove plaster stain before discarding and before applying plaster.	33	27	60
13) Apply sterile dressing with fresh paste of forceps.			
14) Discard forceps and apply strappings.	22	38	60
15) Place dressing towel and mackintosh.	48	12	60
16) Replace all lids.	60	0	60
17) Leave patient comfortable.	60	0	60
18) Return screens and open windows.	20	40	60
19) Clear trolley.	57	3	60
	49	11	60
TOTAL	53	7	60
	793	347	1140

dressing with a fresh paste of forceps. All (60) respondents used dressing towels and mackintosh and discarded forceps and applied strappings. Twenty (33.3%) of the respondents replaced all lids, 57(95%) made patient comfortable before leaving patient bed side. Windows were opened and screens returned by 49(81.7%) of respondents and 53(88.3%) of respondents cleared trolley after the procedure. This result shows a very good performance of wound dressing procedure of the nursing personnel as over 69% of procedures were carried out correctly with mean performance of procedure as 13. 9.

Table 3: Group statistics

Procedure performance	Male +	Female -	Total
Yes	13.9	13.8	27.70
No	5.10	5.0	10.30
Total	19.00	8.60	38.00

$$X^2 = \frac{n(ad-bc)^2}{efgh}$$

$$X^2 = \frac{38(72.28 - 70.38)^2}{5420.89}$$

$$X^2 = 0.02$$

Hypothesis 1

Table 3 showed the mean performance of wound dressing by males and females as 13.9 for males and 13.8 for females. The calculated chi-square value of 0.02 is not significant at 95% confidence interval hence the hypothesis that says there will be no significant difference in the performance of wound dressing by males and females is accepted.

Table 4: Association of Educational Background

Educational qualification	Mean difference	Standard error	Sig.	95% Confidence interval	
				Lower boundary	Upper boundary
Nursing students and registered nurses.	2.6279	.8296	.002	.9650	4.2889
Nursing students and registered nurse – midwife	1.0714	.9851	.282	-.9032	3.0461
Nursing student and BSc. /BNSc. holders.	7.1432	1.3498	.958	-.6325	2.7754

Hypothesis 11

Table 4 showed the mean difference of the educational background of respondents at 95% interval. The mean difference between nursing students and registered nurse / midwife is 2.6270 with standard error of 0.8296 and significance of 0.002. The mean difference is significant at 0.05 levels which mean there is significant difference in the performance of wound dressing between student nurses and registered nurses. Hence the hypothesis that says there will be no significant difference between student nurses and registered nurses is rejected.

Table 5

Educational qualification	Mean difference	Standard error	Sig.	95% Confidence interval	
				Lower boundary	Upper boundary
BSc / BNSc. Holders					
Nursing students	-7.1429	1.3498	.958	-2.7754	2.6325
Registered nurse / midwife	2.5556	1.5057	.095	-4608	5.5719
Registered Nurse - midwife	1.0000	1.5971	.534	-2,1993	4.1993

Hypothesis III

There will be no relationship between performance of surgical wound dressing procedure and educational background of nurses.

Table 5 shows the mean difference of educational background of respondents in this study at a confidence interval of 95%. Comparing University graduates to the other respondents the mean differences are as follows;

Nursing students -7.1429

Registered Nurse / Midwife 2.5556

Registered Nurse-Midwife 1.0000

The mean differences are not significant at 0.05 levels so the hypothesis that says there will be no relationship between performance of surgical wound dressing procedure and educational background of nurses is accepted.

DISCUSSION

This research was conducted to assess the performance of wound dressing by nursing personnel in Olabisi Onabanjo University Teaching hospital (O.O.U.T.H) Shagamu Ogun State. The result shows a very good performance of wound dressing by the nursing personnel with a mean performance of 13.9. This is worth noting as it disagrees with previous studies conducted among nurses regarding procedure performance.

However, the result indicates that 45% of respondents did not wash their hands before carrying out wound dressing. This agrees with reports by the New England journal of medicine that lacks of hand washing remains at an unacceptable level in most medical environments with large number of nurses and doctors routinely are forgetting to wash their hands before coming in contact with patients. (Goldman, 2006). In an observational study which analysed the quality of wound dressing procedure performed on hospitalized patients at a medical surgical unit of a university teaching hospital, it was observed that the habit of hand washing or use of alcohol gel is not incorporated as an important nursing action in the prevention of risks for patients and employees.

Studies in Brazilian literature also identified that hand washing before and after the execution of nursing procedure is deficient, exposing the patient to hospital acquired infection risk. Hand hygiene is a single most effective activity for reducing infections but evidence suggests that many health professionals do not decontaminate their hands as often as they need to and most nurses do not use correct hand washing techniques. A study showed that proper hand washing and other simple procedures can decrease the rate of catheter related blood stream infections by 66%.(Pronovost, Needlan, Berenholtz *et al* 2006).

International studies identifies low adherence to hand washing by health professionals as; disbelief in the risk of pathogen transmission, negligence lack of material and difficult access to alcohol gel dispensers. Since the purpose of hand washing in the health care setting is to remove or minimize pathogenic microorganism and avoid transmitting them, this aspect of the dressing procedure should be given attention to avoid wound contamination during dressing.

CONCLUSION

In the assessment of wound dressing by nursing personnel in O.O.U.T.H. Shagamu, it was observed from the data analysis that nurses have very good performance of wound dressing procedure. Wound dressing performance is not dependent on gender, educational qualification or years of experience of the nursing personnel. Performance of wound dressing depends on commitment to work ethics, availability of the necessary equipment and materials. Short cuts which could affect the wound healing process were taken due to unavailability of equipment and nursing personnel. The result showed very good performance of wound dressing by nursing personnel in O.O.U.T.H. Shagamu but good hand washing practice is deficient. Wound management involves a comprehensive care plan with consideration of all factors contributing to and affecting

the wound and the patient. Although no single discipline can meet the needs of a patient with a wound but the best outcomes are generated by dedicated, well-educated personnel from multiple discipline working together for the common goal of holistic patient care.

RECOMMENDATION

- 1) Regular seminars on the management of wound should be organized for nursing personnel to keep them up to date on various techniques of wound dressing and wound dressing materials.
- 2) Patients should be educated on the physiology of wound healing and early signs of various complications of wound especially infection because with this knowledge patient will be able to cooperate with the nursing personnel in his care in order to improve the healing process.
- 3) Student nurses should be educated on proper wound dressing techniques both at school and during the clinical postings in the hospital.
- 4) Government and non-governmental organizations should come to the aid of this institution by providing wound dressing equipment, employment/training of nursing personnel who are specialized in wound.

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